

Does Metacognition and Science Process Skills Affect the Managerial Ability of Leaders in Islamic Boarding Schools?

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ABSTRACT: This study aims to identify and measure the effect of metacognition and science process skills on the educational managerial abilities of leaders at Pondok Pesantren Salaf API Tegalrejo Magelang. The approach used in this study is exploratory quantitative. The instrument used in this study was a questionnaire, which was a questionnaire consisting of 30 questions for each variable as measured by Likert scale answers. The sample used in this study was all leaders, from the highest to the lowest, totaling 38 people. Furthermore, the data that has been collected is analyzed in two stages, namely: 1) the analysis stage of identifying categories for each variable and 2) the stage of statistical correlation testing. Based on the data that has been obtained and the discussion, it can be understood that metacognition and SPS have a positive effect on the ability of the leadership of the Salaf API Islamic boarding school in conducting educational management at each level of leadership with a correlation level of 0.820 and 0.718 respectively. In addition, both variables together also have a positive effect on the leadership's ability to carry out managerial education, namely 0.780. Thus, this study proves that the managerial abilities of leaders of Islamic educational institutions are strongly influenced by metacognition and science process skills. Therefore, the implication of this research is that improving the educational managerial abilities of leaders in Islamic boarding schools can be carried out by developing metacognition-based training programs and science process skills.

Keywords: Metacognition, Science Process Skills, Educational Management Innovation.

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1. Introduction

Efforts to improve the quality of education are still a hot discussion in almost all countries in the world. In Indonesia, efforts to improve the quality of education have been, are being and continue to be carried out by leaders and remain a major issue in the presidential election process from year to year. The quality of education is closely related to the quality of management carried out by the leaders of educational institutions. The better the quality of management of educational institutions, the better the quality of education in

general. This was also conveyed by Matorera (2018), Mukhsin (2019), Kuntoro (2019) and Girmanová, et al. (2022), improving the quality of education can be done by properly applying management principles. Firdianti (2018) and Loeung & Safruddin (2021) in their research also stated that implementing school-based management can improve student achievement. In addition, Asmara & Nindianti (2019), Horne (2022), and Jamba & Norbu (2023) also explain that (classroom) management is very important for achieving learning goals. Therefore, efforts to improve the quality of education can be started by improving and increasing the quality of management of the education system itself, both at the class level, schools and foundations, and other larger organizations.

Education in the global era requires relatively more challenging management than before (Benson, 2018) and (Čulková, et al.2021). This is because the global era, apart from demanding the success of achieving quality education in general, also requires education to be in line with global developments. Mukti (2019) and Atta Quainoo et al., (2022) state that education in the global era must be able to prepare students with literacy competencies and national character. Suárez-Orozco (2005), Alam (2019), and (Lase, 2019) in their research stated that the global era (industrial revolution 4.0 and the era of Society 5.0) requires students with good problem-solving, critical thinking, and creative abilities. Thus various innovations in the education system must be carried out to ensure the quality of education is maintained and have a positive impact on users in the global era (Ja'far, 2019) and (Rogers, 2022). Various educational innovations must continue to be carried out to follow trends in the field of education sustainably (Gumennykova, et al., 2022) and (Okoye, et al., 2022), for example, the application of an independent curriculum (Hadiapurwa, et al., 2021). Therefore, innovation in the management of the education system in the global era is a necessity.

Unfortunately, efforts to increase the managerial capacity of the leaders of educational institutions in Indonesia in general have not been optimally successful. Most of the innovations to improve the managerial capabilities of educational institution leaders are carried out through a top-down policy approach. Various training programs to improve the managerial capabilities of educational institution leaders are still prepared for the general public and are in the form of dissemination of policies developed by the government. Likewise, the reference indicators of leadership managerial success are also measured by the instruments in the policy. The result is that the success of improving the quality of education is still limited to reports that are adjusted to the demands of the instruments in the policy and have not yet touched on the main issues.

One of the educational institutions that require innovation in the management of the education system is Islamic boarding schools. Islamic boarding schools have an important role in preparing a quality generation in this global era (Tan & Bodovski, 2020; Mita & Ashif, 2020; Ijah, et al. 2021; Susilawati & Misbah, 2022; Anam Besari, 2022). Innovation in education management at Islamic boarding schools is intended so that Islamic boarding schools must have the ability to prepare quality students (santri), be able to compete in the job market, be professional in doing their jobs and not lose their identity as a Muslim (Suparno, 2018; Sadali, 2020; Kariyanto, 2020; Pramana, et al. 2021; Revati et al. 2022; Amet, 2023). These efforts can only be carried out if the leaders at the Islamic boarding school can carry out various management innovations or managerial capabilities that can guarantee the implementation of a quality educational process.

Leadership in educational institutions has a very important position. Leaders in educational institutions greatly influence the quality of education (Ekosiswoyo, 2016; Said, 2018; Kurniawati, et al., 2020; Kapoor et al., 2022; Rozaq, et al., 2022; Khalid Arar and Izhar, 2022). The success of the leadership of educational institutions is greatly influenced and determined by their managerial abilities (Ting, et al., 2021; Francis, et al., 2022; Edi & Wijaya, 2022; Lee, Kim, & Kim, 2023). Therefore, efforts to improve the managerial capabilities of the leaders of educational institutions through various types of research are a

must. This is done to ensure the quality of education in the future (Gilli, Lettner, & Guettel, 2023).

The ability of leaders (including leaders at Islamic boarding schools) in carrying out their duties is generally influenced by many factors, both internal and external factors. Externally, a person's managerial ability is influenced by environmental situations and conditions, while internally it is influenced by his ability to think, behave and act. Even Martínez-Hague (2017) states that various innovations in the field of education start with the critical thinking of its leaders. Several theories state that internal factors (personal abilities) play a greater role in success. This is as mentioned by Naisabur & Kiki (2022) and (Chen et al., 2023) that internal factors of one's personality influence one's leadership style. The results of this study were also reinforced by the statements of Rahayu & Agustina (2022), He (2023) and Ranjeeni, et al., (2023) a person's psychological state greatly influences his leadership abilities.

Good leadership skills are often associated with managerial abilities. The better the managerial ability, the better the leadership ability. This is in line with research (Hoffman & Shipper, 2012; Sonmez & Adiguzel 2020; and Sugiyanto & Ruknan, 2020) that leadership and managerial skills are closely related and have a positive effect on employee performance and institutional performance. In the field of education, the managerial ability also has a positive effect on teacher performance (Islamia, 2021; Muniroh, et al. 2022 and Sartika, et al., 2023). Meanwhile, good teacher performance will determine education and learning in general and student achievement or learning outcomes (Ningsih & Isjoni, 2021; Lenny S. Songcayawon et al., 2022; Krisnayanti & Wijaya, 2022) as well as student motivation (Rahmawati, 2023). Therefore it can be understood that the managerial ability of the leaders of educational institutions is also closely related to the quality of education in general.

Many factors affect a person's managerial ability. One of the internal factors (personal ability) that are thought to influence the managerial ability of the leaders of educational institutions is metacognition. This ability is closely related to the skills of thinking, planning, implementing, and assessing something and greatly influences a person's self-efficacy and adaptation (Joie-La Marle, et al., 2023), including in influencing scientific attitudes (Biscocho, 2021) and awareness to do or not doing something (Jennifer & Charles, 2023). This is as explained by Ainun, et al. (2019) that metacognition is a person's awareness of using and controlling his thoughts. Asy'ari, et al. (2018), Humairah (2020), Rivas, et al. (2022) and Drigas, et al. (2023) stated that metacognition is one of the higher-order thinking skills that play an important role in shaping one's independence. Several other studies also state that metacognitive abilities greatly determine a person's success in doing something, for example, problem solving (Setyaningrum, 2020), success in learning (Abdullah, 2018; Usman, et al., 2018; Anindya, et al., 2019), creative thinking (Rohman, et al. 2018). Therefore, metacognition is also strongly suspected to be closely related to the management tasks of a leader.

The urgency of metacognition in managerial processes by a leader of an educational institution has not been fully paid attention to. This can be seen from the relatively few studies linking metacognitive abilities to managerial abilities. Several related studies have recently linked leadership and self-regulation (Asisdiq, et al., 2017), and even then with a relatively small number. The research linking metacognition abilities and leadership is also still very limited. Several related studies, for example, were carried out by Mango, et al. (2019) who examined the carrying capacity of metacognition abilities to leadership development. Meanwhile, Kontostavlou & Drigas (2021) in their research explains metacognition that supports the development of one's leadership talents. Kim, (2019) plays a role in one's metacognition and emotional intelligence in leading himself. In general, none of the studies above have been able to answer how strong the role or influence of metacognition is on a person's managerial abilities, especially the leadership of

educational institutions. This has an impact on the absence of various training programs to improve the managerial skills of leaders of metacognition-based educational institutions.

In addition to metacognition abilities, other skills needed to achieve success in carrying out their duties are science process skills. This skill is closely related to one's ability to make observations, collect and analyze data and make reports (Putri & Muhartati, 2019; Rahma, et al., 2020; Majeed, et al., 2023). In addition, it can also be said that SPS is a person's ability to apply the scientific method for decision-making (Samitra & Kristiawan, 2016; Ediyanto, et al., 2018). Science process skills are very important for developing 21st-century skills (Astuti et al., 2021; Elmas & Saban, 2018). Some research results state that SPS has a positive effect on one's achievement, for example on learning outcomes (Isticharoh, 2019; Ischak, et al., 2020), critical thinking skills (Fitria, 2021), creative thinking skills (Darmaji, et al., 2022). Therefore, this ability is also closely related to the success of an educational institution leader in carrying out his managerial duties.

The importance of SPS in supporting one's success in everyday life as described above has not been fully verified empirically, especially about one's managerial abilities. Research related to the relationship between science process skills and the managerial abilities of leaders of educational institutions is still relatively few and limited. This is because these skills are closely considered part of the field of science education and are not related to the field of management. Therefore research related to the relationship between these two variables needs to be carried out to see how far the role of science process skills influences someone in carrying out their managerial tasks.

Referring to the description above, structured and systematic research is needed to provide empirical information on how metacognition abilities and science process skills influence the managerial abilities of leaders of educational institutions, especially in the API Tegalrejo Islamic boarding school environment, Magelang. The results of this study will provide a new perspective on the factors supporting the success of an educational institution leader in carrying out his managerial duties. In addition, the results of this study also contribute to providing ideas about the development of training models to improve managerial skills for leaders of educational institutions in general.

2. Method

The approach used in this study is exploratory quantitative. The instrument used in this study was a questionnaire, which was a questionnaire consisting of 30 questions for each variable as measured by Likert scale answers. The sample used in this study was all leaders, from the highest to the lowest, totaling 38 people. This sample includes unit heads, vice principals (MTs, SMA, MA), and school principals.

The variable measured in this study is metacognition ability (X1) with the measurement aspect referring to the opinions of Sukarno & Widdah (2020) and Sukarno & Musyafa, (2021) including: (1) Declarative Knowledge (DK), (2) Procedural Knowledge (PK), (3) Conditional knowledge (CK), (4) Cognition Regulation (CR), (5) Information Management System (IMS), (6) Monitoring Understanding (MU), (7) Correction strategy (CS) and (8) Self-evaluation skills (SES). The SPS variable (X2) refers to the opinion of Mahmudah, et al. (2019), Khairunnisa, et al. (2020), and (Darmayanti & Setiawati, 2022), which include: (1) the ability to observe or observe, (2) classify, (3) collect information or data, (4) associate or process data, and (5) communicate or make a report. Meanwhile, the managerial ability variable (Y) measured in this study refers to the opinions of Rupnidah & Eliza, (2022), High (2022), and Muniroh et al. (2022) including (1) the ability to plan, (2) organize or manage, (3) implement the plans that have been made, and (4) the ability to supervise. Each measured variable has been set (adjusted with indicators) in such a way as to obtain a maximum score of 100 points and a minimum score of 25.

Furthermore, based on the data that has been obtained, it is then analyzed in two stages, namely: 1) the analysis stage of identifying categories for each variable and 2) the

statistical correlation test stage. In this study, the correlation test was carried out with the help of SPSS 16 software. This was intended to maintain the accuracy of the data and the results of the analysis.

3. Results and Discussion

Measurement of each variable in this study was carried out in a structured and systematic manner and stages. As mentioned earlier, the variables in this study include metacognition abilities, science process skills, and managerial abilities of the leaders at the Salaf API Tegal Rejo Islamic Boarding School, Malang. After the necessary data is collected, then it is analyzed. The results of the first stage of the analysis show that the metacognition abilities, SPS, and managerial abilities of the leaders in the Islamic boarding school environment vary, some are in the "high", "medium" and "low" categories. The results of the first stage of analysis in more detail can be seen in Table 1 below:

Table 1. Category Analysis of Metacognitive Ability, SPS, and Managerial Ability of Leaders in the Salaf API Tegal Rejo Islamic Boarding School, Malang

Variables	Score	Number of Respondents	Percentage (%)	Category
Metacognition	76-100	15	39,47	High
	51-75	17	44,74	Moderate
	25-50	6	15,79	Low
	Total	38	100	
SPS	76-100	14	36,84	High
	51-75	15	39,47	Moderate
	25-50	9	23,68	Low
	Total	38	100	
Managerial Ability	76-100	16	42,10	High
	51-75	14	36,84	Moderate
	25-50	8	21,05	Low
	Total	38	100	

Based on Table 1 above, it can be understood that the metacognitive ability of the leaders in the Salaf API Tegal Rejo Islamic Boarding School environment is in a row the "high" category, which is as much as 39.47%, the "moderate" category is 44.74%, and the rest as much as 15.79% are in the "low" category. As for the SPS variables, namely: the "high" category was 36.84%, the "moderate" category was 39.47% and the remaining 23.68% were in the "low" category. Whereas in the managerial ability variable, the "high" category was 42.10%, the "moderate" category was 36.84% and the "low" category was 21.05%. Therefore, referring to the existing data, it can be said that in general, the ability of the leaders in the API Tegal Rejo Islamic Boarding School environment in all three aspects/variables is quite good.

Table 2. Correlation between Metacognition, SPS, and Managerial Ability variables

		Metacognition	SPS	Managerial Ability
Metacognition	Pearson Correlation	1	.820**	.660**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000
	N	38	38	38
SPS	Pearson Correlation	.820**	1	.718**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000
	N	38	30	38
Managerial Ability	Pearson Correlation	.660**	.718**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	
	N	38	38	39

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 3. Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. The error in the Estimate
1	.780 ^a	.608	.638	1.391

a. Predictors: (Constant), SPS, Metacognition

Based on the Summary model table above, the calculated R-value is 0.780 > from the R table, namely 0.320 (for n=38 it is 0.320 with a significance of 5%). This shows that there is a significant contribution between variables X1 (metacognition) and X2 (SPS) with variable Y (Managerial Ability). Thus it can be said that 78% of the managerial skills of the leaders in the API Tegal Rejo Salaf Islamic Boarding School are influenced by metacognition abilities and SPS abilities, and the remaining 22% are influenced by other factors.

Table 4. Model ANOVAb

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	
1	Regression	788.297	2	344.149	213.111	.000 ^a
	Residual	65.322	35	1.419		
	Total	843.619	37			

a. Predictors: (Constant), SPS, Metacognition

b. Dependent Variable: Managerial Ability

Based on the ANOVA table above, it is known that the sig. 0.000 which means less than (<) 0.05, it can be said that X1 (Metacognition) and X2 (SPS) simultaneously affect variable Y (Managerial Ability). This is also reinforced by the calculated F value of 213.111 > F table 3.22. This means that the two variables, namely X1 and X2 simultaneously affect the variable Y (Managerial Ability).

Based on the data that has been obtained and the discussion, it can be understood that metacognition and SPS have a positive effect on the ability of the leadership of the Salaf API Islamic boarding school in conducting educational management at each level of leadership with a correlation level of 0.820 and 0.718 respectively. In addition, both variables together also have a positive effect on the leadership's ability to innovate in education management, namely 0.780. Thus, this research implies that increasing the ability to innovate the educational management of leaders can be done by developing programs based on metacognition and science process skills.

4. Discussion

The results of the research above show that metacognition has empirically proven to have a significant effect on managerial ability or the ability to manage educational institution leaders. The results of this study also prove that a person's managerial abilities and success are largely determined and influenced by metacognition abilities which reach 82%. This means that the better a person's metacognitive ability, the better his managerial ability. Meanwhile, good managerial skills will have a positive impact on the quality of education services in the institutions they lead (Irsyadiyah, 2020) and (Ulil Albab, 2021), including improving performance (Laghari & Hussain, 2022), the effectiveness of teaching teachers (Silva, 2021) as well as on teacher professionalism in general (Riyadi et al., 2023) and (Hill, Hains, & Hains, 2023). Managerial ability will also have a positive impact on management innovation in an organization or institution (Costa, et al., 2023). So in other words it can also be said that the better the metacognitive ability of a leader of an

educational institution, the quality of education at the educational institution will also be better.

The positive relationship between metacognitive abilities and managerial abilities of educational institution leaders as the results of this study can be well understood. This is based on a theory that leadership is an activity of influencing someone in the form of instructions, orders, or actions to achieve goals through communication channels (Ibarra, 2021) and (Habe et al., 2022). Meanwhile, each of these activities always involves the ability to think and mental activity (Saini & Shabnam, 2021) and (Chero, 2023). The ability to think and think activities are a major part of metacognition (Amin, et al., 2020) and (Willis, et al., 2023). This is as mentioned by U. Albab, et al. (2020) and Yasinta, et al. (2023) that metacognition is a mental activity that is carried out consciously in a cognitive structure that allows someone to help them control, organize, and analyze their thoughts. Therefore why metacognition ability plays a big role in the managerial ability of a leader, can be understood from this point of view.

The results of the study imply that the development of managerial capabilities of educational institution leaders, especially at the Salaf API Islamic Boarding School in Tegal Rejo, Malang, can be carried out by considering their metacognition. Therefore, it is necessary to carry out training to improve the managerial abilities of the leaders of these educational institutions with an orientation based on the development of metacognition. Some activities or training that have the potential to develop metacognition abilities according to experts can be used as a guide for the development of metacognition-based training models for leaders of educational institutions including training on experimental learning models (Febriyanni & Santika, 2022), training with a metacognitive approach, namely orientation of thinking skills and self-reflection (Pertiwi, et al., 2022), training using the PQ4R metacognitive approach, namely Preview, Question, Read, Reflect, Recite, and Review (Nur' Afifah, 2022).

As previously mentioned by Sukarno & Widdah (2020) and Sukarno & Musyafa, (2021) that there are several aspects of metacognition, namely: (1) Declarative Knowledge (DK), (2) Procedural Knowledge (PK), (3) Conditional knowledge (CK), (4) Cognition Regulation (CR), (5) Information Management System (IMS), (6) Monitoring Understanding (MU), (7) Correction strategy (CS) and (8) Self-evaluation skills (SES), which was measured in this research is strongly suspected that each influences different managerial abilities. However, this study has not explained how the role of each of these aspects influences the managerial abilities of the leaders of educational institutions. Therefore, it is necessary to conduct further research to find out and answer this problem.

In addition, referring to the results of this study (Table 2), it can be seen that SPS affects the managerial ability of leaders in the Salaf API Tegal Rejo Islamic Boarding School, Malang by 71.8% in the "significant" category. This shows that SPS has an important role in the success of leaders in carrying out their managerial duties. Therefore, this study proves that SPS has a positive effect on one's success, both in the academic field and in other areas of life. This is because SPS is also closely related to critical thinking skills (Fitria, 2021) and (Agnes, et al., 2022), creative thinking (Darmaji et al., 2022), and problem-solving and program development skills (Roa & Fajardo, 2022). The ability to think, creativity and problem-solving skills are very closely related to managerial success.

Seeing the positive relationship or correlation between SPS and the managerial abilities of the heads of educational institutions (Table 2) above, it can be said that an increase in the SPS of leaders also means an increase in managerial abilities. It also means that efforts to improve the managerial capabilities of educational institution leaders can be carried out by developing SPS capacity building. Some experts state that increasing the SPS itself can be done with several activity approaches, including outdoor/gardening activities (Mirawati & Nugraha, 2017), hands-on activity-based discussions (Avisya, et al., 2019), training or learning based on STAD (Komikesari, 2016). It's just about improving and developing the managerial capabilities of the leaders of educational institutions, these

activities need to be modified so that they are by the situation and conditions of the leaders of educational institutions as training participants.

As previously mentioned, the science process skills measured in this study include aspects of 1) the ability to observe or observe, (2) classify, (3) collect information or data, (4) associate or process data, and (5) communicate or make a report. However, this research has not elaborated and answered the question of which aspect plays the most role in influencing the managerial abilities of the leaders of these educational institutions and which aspects are less important? This is because this research focuses on looking at and answering questions about how SPS influences general managerial abilities. Therefore, further research is needed on the role of each aspect of SPS that plays the most role and plays the least role.

Taking into account the results of this study, especially in Table 4, namely that metacognition ability and SPS jointly affect the managerial abilities of the leaders at the Salaf API Tegal Rejo Islamic Boarding School, in the development of the training model it is also necessary to consider these two variables together. This is intended so that the achievement of the objectives, namely increasing the managerial capabilities of the leaders is more optimal. Optimum managerial abilities of the leaders of educational institutions with training based on metacognition and SPS will also have a positive impact on improving the quality of education in general.

5. Conclusion

Based on the data that has been obtained and the discussion, it can be understood that metacognition and SPS have a positive effect on the ability of the leadership of the Salaf API Islamic boarding school in conducting educational management at each level of leadership with a correlation level of 0.820 and 0.718 respectively. In addition, both variables together also have a positive effect on the leadership's ability to carry out managerial education, namely 0.780. Thus, this research implies that increasing the managerial ability of educational leaders in the Salaf API Tegal Rejo Islamic boarding school can be carried out by developing programs based on metacognition and science process skills. In addition, based on the ANOVA table above, it is known that the sig. 0.000 which means less than ($<$) 0.05, it can be said that X1 (Metacognition) and X2 (SPS) simultaneously affect variable Y (Managerial Ability). This means that the two variables, namely X1 and X2 simultaneously affect the variable Y (Managerial Ability).

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References

1. Abdullah, R. (2018). Urgensi Metakognisi Dalam Pencapaian Hasil Belajar Kimia Di SMA. Lantanida Journal. <https://doi.org/10.22373/lj.v5i2.2834>
2. Agnes Aktapianti Br. Ginting, Darmaji, D., & Dwi Agus Kurniawan. (2022). Analisis

- Pentingnya Keterampilan Proses Sains terhadap Kemampuan Berpikir Kritis di SMA Se-Kecamatan Pemayung. *Jurnal Pendidikan Mipa*, 12(1), 91–96. <https://doi.org/10.37630/jpm.v12i1.542>
3. Ainun Fauziah, H., Putri Setyowati, A., Dewantari, R., Dwi Wulandari, A., & Adi Prayitno, B. (2019). Profil Kesadaran Metakognisi Siswa di salah satu SMA Swasta di Sragen. *BIOSFER: Jurnal Biologi Dan Pendidikan Biologi*. <https://doi.org/10.23969/biosfer.v3i2.975>
 4. Alam, S. (2019). Higher Order Thinking Skills (HOTS): Kemampuan Memecahkan Masalah, Berpikir Kritis dan Kreatif dalam Pendidikan Seni untuk Menghadapi Revolusi Industri 4.0 pada Era Society 5.0. *Prosiding Seminar Nasional Pascasarjana (PROSNAMPAS)*, 2(1), 790–797.
 5. Albab, U., Budiyo, & Indriati, D. (2020). Metacognition skills and higher order thinking skills (HOTS) in mathematics. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 1613(1). <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1613/1/012017>
 6. Albab, Ulil. (2021). Perencanaan Pendidikan dalam Manajemen Mutu Terpadu Pendidikan Islam. *PANCAR*, 5(1), 119–126.
 7. Amet. (2023). Enrichment: Journal of Management Transformation of Islamic educational institutions in realizing quality human resources in the global era. *Enrichment: Journal of Management*, 12(6).
 8. Amin, A. M., Corebima, A. D., Zubaidah, S., & Mahanal, S. (2020). The correlation between metacognitive skills and critical thinking skills at the implementation of four different learning strategies in animal physiology lectures. *European Journal of Educational Research*, 9(1), 143–163. <https://doi.org/10.12973/eu-jer.9.1.143>
 9. Anam Besari. (2022). Efektivitas Pondok Pesantren Dalam Pembentukan Karakter Anak. *Paradigma*, 13(1), 82–94.
 10. Anindya, I. A. W., Mahrus, M., & Hadiprayitno, G. (2019). Hubungan Kemampuan Metakognisi Siswa Dengan Hasil Belajar Ipa Melalui Penerapan Model Pembelajaran Berbasis Masalah Di SMP Negeri 2 Kuripan. *Jurnal Pendidikan Biologi*. <https://doi.org/10.17977/um052v10i2p66-73>
 11. Asisdiq, I., Sudding, & Side, S. (2017). Self-Regulated Learning Dalam Kepemimpinan Mahasiswa Pendidikan Ulama Tarjih Muhammadiyah. *Pendidikan Kimia PPs UNM*, 1(1), 91–99.
 12. Asmara, Y., & Nindianti, D. S. (2019). Urgensi Manajemen Kelas Untuk Mencapai Tujuan Pembelajaran. *SINDANG: Jurnal Pendidikan Sejarah Dan Kajian Sejarah*. <https://doi.org/10.31540/sdg.v1i1.192>
 13. Astuti, F. O., Biologi, D. P., Sukabumi, U. M., Ji, R., No, S. H., Biologi, M. P., ... No, S. H. (2021). Mengajarkan Keterampilan Proses Sains Dalam Pembelajaran Jarak Jauh. *BIO-EDU: Jurnal Pendidikan Biologi*, 6(2), 74–82.
 14. Asy'ari, M., Ikhsan, M., & Muhali, M. (2018). Apa Itu Metakognisi dan Mengapa Penting? *Seminar Nasional Lembaga Penelitian Dan Pendidikan (LPP) Mandala*, (September), 1–14.
 15. Atta Quainoo, E., Aggrey, R., Aggrey, D., Adams, F., Opoku, E., & Wanzam Abubakari, Z. (2022). The Impact of Globalization on Education: A Blessing or a Curse. *Education Journal*, 11(2), 70. <https://doi.org/10.11648/j.edu.20221102.13>
 16. Avisya, N., Miriam, S., & Suyidno, S. (2019). Penerapan Model Pembelajaran Kooperatif Berbasis Hands on Activity untuk Meningkatkan Keterampilan Proses Sains. *Jurnal Ilmiah Pendidikan Fisika*. <https://doi.org/10.20527/jjpf.v3i3.1036>
 17. Benson, L. (2018). Leadership skills in the digital age: Implications for university business schools. *Journal of Eastern European and Central Asian Research*, 5(2), 80–89. <https://doi.org/10.15549/jeecar.v5i2.217>
 18. Biscocho, S. S. (2021). Metacognitive Knowledge, Skills, and Attitude of Science Metacognitive Knowledge, Skills and Attitude of Science Technology and Society Students Across Programs. *Luz y Saber*, 15(1), 5–14.
 19. Chen, S., Fan, M., Wang, X., Fan, Y., Chen, S. T., & Ren, S. (2023). Managerial ability, compensation incentives, and corporate performance. *Frontiers in Environmental Science*, 11(March), 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fenvs.2023.1074159>
 20. Chero, C. A. . (2023). The Impact of Metacognitive Instruction on EFL Low-level Learners'

- Listening Performance and Metacognitive Awareness. *International Journal of Instruction*, 16(2), 291–306. Retrieved from www.e-iji.net
21. Costa, J., Pádua, M., & Moreira, A. C. (2023). Leadership Styles and Innovation Management: What Is the Role of Human Capital? *Administrative Sciences*, 13(2). <https://doi.org/10.3390/admsci13020047>
 22. Čulková, K., Hrehová, D., Seňová, A., & Teplická, K. (2021). Managerial skills in the globalized world in chosen EU countries. *SHS Web of Conferences*, 129, 02003. <https://doi.org/10.1051/shsconf/202112902003>
 23. Darmaji, Astalini, Dwi Agus Kurniawan, & Bob Widodi. (2022). The Relationship Between Science Process Skills and Students' Creative Thinking Skills on Magnetism in Junior High School. *Jurnal Pedagogi Dan Pembelajaran*, 5(3), 492–500. <https://doi.org/10.23887/jp2.v5i3.48636>
 24. Darmayanti, N. W. S., & Setiawati, N. W. I. (2022). Analisis Keterampilan Proses Sains Siswa Kelas VI di SD N 1 Cempaga. *Jurnal Pendidikan Dan Pembelajaran Sains Indonesia (JPPSI)*, 5(2), 119–127. <https://doi.org/10.23887/jppsi.v5i2.52638>
 25. Drigas, A., Mitsea, E., & Skianis, C. (2023). Meta-Learning: A Nine-Layer Model Based on Metacognition and Smart Technologies. *Sustainability*, 15(2), 1668. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su15021668>
 26. Edi, E., & Wijaya, E. (2022). The Role of Managerial Ability on Operational Performance and Stock Return Moderated by CEO Overconfidence. *Journal of Accounting Finance and Auditing Studies (JAFAS)*, 258–277. <https://doi.org/10.32602/jafas.2022.036>
 27. Ediyanto, E., Atika, I., Hayashida, M., & Kawai, N. (2018). A Literature Study of Science Process Skill toward Deaf and Hard of Hearing Students. *Advances in Social Science, Education, and Humanities Research*, 218(ICoMSE 2017), 131–136. <https://doi.org/10.2991/icomse-17.2018.23>
 28. Ekosiswoyo, R. (2016). Kepemimpinan Kepala Sekolah yang Efektif Kunci Pencapaian Kualitas Pendidikan. *Jurnal Ilmu Pendidikan*. <https://doi.org/10.17977/jip.v14i2.24>
 29. Elmas, R., & Saban, Y. (2018). The inclusion of science process skills in multiple-choice questions: Are we getting any better? *European Journal of Science and Mathematics Education*, 6(1), 13–23.
 30. Febriyanni, R., & Santika, Z. A. R. (2022). Upaya Meningkatkan Kemampuan Metakognisi Melalui Model Experiential Learning Bidang Studi Al Quran Hadis Di Kelas VIII MTS Nurul Ummi Saodah Kwala *Ability: Journal of ...*, 3(2), 163–175.
 31. Firdianti, A. (2018). Implementasi Manajemen Berbasis Sekolah Dalam Meningkatkan Prestasi Belajar Siswa. In *Implementasi Manajemen Berbasis Sekolah Dalam Meningkatkan Prestasi Belajar Siswa*.
 32. Fitria, D. (2021). Hubungan Keterampilan Proses Sains Dan Kemampuan Berpikir Kritis Padamateri Suhu Dan Kalor. *Journal Evaluation in Education (JEE)*, 1(3), 83–90. <https://doi.org/10.37251/jee.v1i3.137>
 33. Francis, B. B., Sun, X., Weng, C.-H., & Wu, Q. (2022). Managerial ability and tax aggressiveness. *China Accounting and Finance Review*, 24(1), 53–75. <https://doi.org/10.1108/cafr-02-2022-0002>
 34. Gilli, K., Lettner, N., & Guettel, W. (2023). The future of leadership: new digital skills or old analog virtues? *Journal of Business Strategy*, (18133). <https://doi.org/10.1108/JBS-06-2022-0093>
 35. Girmanová, L., Šolc, M., Blaško, P., & Petřík, J. (2022). Quality Management System in Education: Application of Quality Management Models in Educational Organization—Case Study from the Slovak Republic. *Standards*, 2(4), 460–473. <https://doi.org/10.3390/standards2040031>
 36. Gumennykova, T., Ilchenko, P., Bazyl, O., Ilchenko, A., & Vydrych, O. (2022). Educational trends 2022: Essence and innovation potential. *Revista Amazonia Investiga*, 11(55), 226–233. <https://doi.org/10.34069/ai/2022.55.07.24>
 37. Habe, M. J., Samsu Samsu, Mardalina Mardalina, Risatri Gumahansyah, Rusmini Rusmini, Ahdiyenti Ahdiyenti, & Fardinal Fardinal. (2022). Faktor Penentu Keberhasilan Kepemimpinan Pendidikan Islam. *Jurnal Ilmu Multidisplin*, 1(2), 304–313.

- <https://doi.org/10.38035/jim.v1i2.29>
38. Hadiapurwa, A., Riani, P., Yulianti, M. F., & Yuningsih, E. K. (2021). Implementasi Merdeka Belajar untuk Membekali Kompetensi Generasi Muda dalam Menghadapi Era Society 5.0. *Al-Mudarris (Jurnal Ilmiah Pendidikan Islam)*, 4(1), 115–129. <https://doi.org/10.23971/mdr.v4i1.3140>
 39. He, H. (2023). Inventory overproduction and managerial ability. *Journal of Corporate Accounting & Finance*, (January), 1–17. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jcaf.22624>
 40. High, V. (2022). Pengaruh Kemampuan Manajerial Kepala Sekolah Terhadap Kinerja Guru SMKN 3 Enrekang The Director ' s Managerial Abilities Affect The Teacher ' s Performance At. *DECISION : Jurnal Ekonomi Dan Bisnis*, 3, 39–45.
 41. Hill, J., Hains, K., & Hains, B. (2023). International Leadership Development Through Learner-Centered Instruction. *The Journal of Leadership Education*, 22(1). <https://doi.org/10.12806/v22/i1/t1>
 42. Hoffman, R. C., & Shipper, F. M. (2012). The impact of managerial skills on employee outcomes: A cross-cultural study. *International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 23(7), 1414–1435. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09585192.2011.581635>
 43. Horne, S. E. (2022). Classroom management. *British Journal of Teacher Education*, 6(3), 228–235. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0260747800060306>
 44. Humairah, S. N. (2020). Pengaruh Metakognisi, Konsep Diri Dan Kemandirian Belajar Terhadap Kemampuan Pemecahan Masalah Matematika Siswa KelaS XI IPA SMAN 1 GOWA. *Jurnal MSA (Matematika Dan Statistika Serta Aplikasinya)*. <https://doi.org/10.24252/msa.v8i1.12454>
 45. Ibarra, H. (2021). Five Leadership Skills for the Future. *Leader to Leader*, 2021(100), 14–17. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ltl.20557>
 46. Ijah, T., Florentinus, T. S., & Sudana, I. M. (2021). The Quality Assurance of Islamic Boarding School based on Total Quality Management (TQM). *Educational Management*, 10(1), 42–49.
 47. Irsyadiyah, A. (2020). Manajemen Mutu Pendidikan Perpsektif Pendidikan Islam. *Rausyan Fikr : Jurnal Pemikiran Dan Pencerahan*. <https://doi.org/10.31000/rf.v16i1.2459>
 48. Ischak, N. I., Odja, E. A., La Kilo, J., & La Kilo, A. (2020). Pengaruh Keterampilan Proses Sains Melalui Model Inkuiri Terbimbing terhadap Hasil Belajar Siswa pada Materi Larutan Asam Basa. *Hydrogen: Jurnal Kependidikan Kimia*, 8(2), 58. <https://doi.org/10.33394/hjkk.v8i2.2748>
 49. Islamia, Y. Tasya. (2021). Keterampilan Manajerial Kepala Sekolah Dalam Meningkatkan Kinerja Guru Di Masa Pandemi COVID-19 Yolanda Tasya Islamaya Karwanto. *Jurnal Inspirasi Manajemen Pendidikan*, 09 Nomor 0(2), 1123–1139.
 50. Isticharoh, I. (2019). Pengaruh Keterampilan Proses Sains dan Sikap Ilmiah terhadap Prestasi Akademik (Survei SMP Swasta di Jakarta Selatan). *Alfarisi: Jurnal Pendidikan MIPA*, 2(2), 153–158.
 51. Jamba, N., & Norbu, L. (2023). Effective classroom management and students' academic performance: A study in one of the middle secondary schools in Bumthang district. *Polaris Global Journal of Scholarly Research and Trends*, 2(1), 11–25. <https://doi.org/10.58429/pgjsrt.v2n1a112>
 52. Jennifer Aquino Mendoza, & Charles Joshua Trajico Elepaño. (2023). Metacognitive awareness levels of pre-service teachers. *World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews*, 17(3), 365–375. <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2023.17.3.0393>
 53. Joie-La Marle, C., Parmentier, F., Weiss, P.-L., Storme, M., Lubart, T., & Borteyrou, X. (2023). Effects of a New Soft Skills Metacognition Training Program on Self-Efficacy and Adaptive Performance. *Behavioral Sciences*, 13(3), 202. <https://doi.org/10.3390/bs13030202>
 54. Kapoor, G., Bhutani, R., Dutta, M., Sharma, A., Khan, F., & Bhatt, P. (2022). Future Technology-based HPLC Analytical Procedures and Pharmaceutical Description of Empagliflozin. *Journal of Pharmaceutical Negative Results*, 13(November), 1453–1465. <https://doi.org/10.47750/pnr.2022.13.S09.176>
 55. Kariyanto, H. (2020). Peran Pondok Pesantren dalam Masyarakat Modern. *Jurnal*

- Pendidikan “Edukasia Multikultura,” 2(2), 67–82.
56. Khairunnisa, K., Ita, I., & Istiqamah, I. (2020). Keterampilan Proses Sains (KPS) Mahasiswa Tadris Biologi pada Mata Kuliah Biologi Umum. *BIO-INOVED: Jurnal Biologi-Inovasi Pendidikan*. <https://doi.org/10.20527/binov.v1i2.7858>
 57. Khalid Arar and Izhar Oplatka. (2022). No Title *Advanced Theories of Educational Leadership. Policy Implications of Research in Education*, XXI(November), 2.
 58. Kim, M. S. (2019). Influence of metacognition and emotional intelligence on self-leadership in nursing students. *Journal of Korean Academy of Nursing Administration*, 25(2), 146–155. <https://doi.org/10.11111/jkana.2019.25.2.146>
 59. Komikesari, H. (2016). Penigkatan Keterampilan Proses Sains dan Hasil Belajar Fisika Siswa pada Model Pembelajaran Kooperatif Tipe Student Team Achievement Division. *Tadris: Jurnal Keguruan Dan Ilmu Tarbiyah*.
 60. Kontostavlou, E. Z., & Drigas, A. (2021). How Metacognition Supports Giftedness in Leadership. *International Journal of Advanced Corporate Learning (IJAC)*, 14(2), 4–16. <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijac.v14i2.23237>
 61. Krisnayanti, I. G. A. A. H., & Wijaya, S. (2022). Pengaruh Kinerja Guru Terhadap Hasil Belajar Siswa Kelas 5 SD Mata Pelajaran Science Sekolah XYZ. *Jurnal Ilmiah Mandala Education*, 8(2), 1776–1785. <https://doi.org/10.58258/jime.v8i2.3313>
 62. Kuntoro, A. T. (2019). Manajemen Mutu Pendidikan Islam. *Jurnal Kependidikan*. <https://doi.org/10.24090/jk.v7i1.2928>
 63. Kurniawati, E., Arafat, Y., & Puspita, Y. (2020). Peran Kepemimpinan Kepala Sekolah dalam Meningkatkan Mutu Pendidikan melalui Manajemen Berbasis Sekolah. *Journal of Education Research*. <https://doi.org/10.37985/joe.v1i2.12>
 64. Laghari, M. A., & Hussain Jafri, D. I. (2022). Headteachers' Managerial Skills and Teachers' Performance at Public Secondary Schools. *International Research Journal of Education and Innovation*, 3(1), 66–75. [https://doi.org/10.53575/irjei.v3.01.7\(22\)66-75](https://doi.org/10.53575/irjei.v3.01.7(22)66-75)
 65. Lase, D. (2019). Pendidikan di Era Revolusi Industri 4.0. *SUNDERMANN Jurnal Ilmiah Teologi Pendidikan Sains Humaniora Dan Kebudayaan*. <https://doi.org/10.36588/sundermann.v1i1.18>
 66. Lee, J., Kim, S., & Kim, E. (2023). The effect of managerial ability on voluntary disclosure of carbon emissions. *Borsa Istanbul Review*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bir.2023.01.008>
 67. Lenny S. Songcayawon¹, Noeme S. Prieto, Dolorosa T. Ucag, Jean S. Tunguia, Katherine A. Hechanova, Ellen V. Candelario, ... MALABARBAS, G. (2022). Managerial skills of school heads and the performance of teachers: The case of public schools in Antique, Philippines. *Journal of Social Sciences and Management Studies*, 1(2), 77–85. <https://doi.org/10.56556/jssms.v1i2.167>
 68. Loeung, S., & Safruddin, C. (2021). Implementing Quality Management System in School Conflict and Evolution Management. *Proceedings of the 5th International Conference on Current Issues in Education (ICCIE 2021)*, 640(Iccie), 1–6.
 69. Mahmudah, I. R., Makiyah, Y. S., & Sulistyaningsih, D. (2019). Profil Keterampilan Proses Sains (KPS) Siswa SMA di Kota Bandung. *Diffraction*, 1(1), 39–43.
 70. Majeed, S., Yasmin, F., & Ahmad, R. (2023). Inquiry-Based Instruction and Students' Science Process Skills: An Experimental Study Abstract: Keywords: Pakistan *Journal of Social Sciences (PJSS)*, 43(1), 155–166.
 71. Mango, E., Koshal, J., & Ouma, C. (2019). Metacognitive Ability Effect on Leadership Development. *Integrated Journal of Business and Economics*, 3(3), 279. <https://doi.org/10.33019/ijbe.v3i3.232>
 72. Martínez-Hague, P. (2017). Educating innovative and critical-thinking managers. *360: Revista de Ciencias de La Gestión*, (2), 30–45. <https://doi.org/10.18800/360gestion.201702.002>
 73. Moreira, D. (2018). Quality Management Systems in Education. *Quality Management Systems - a Selective Presentation of Case-Studies Showcasing Its Evolution*. <https://doi.org/10.5772/intechopen.71431>
 74. Mirawati, M., & Nugraha, R. (2017). Meningkatkan Keterampilan Proses Sains Anak Usia Dini Melalui Aktivitas Berkebun. *Early Childhood: Jurnal Pendidikan*, 1(1), 13–27.

- <https://doi.org/10.35568/earlychildhood.v1i1.50>
75. Mita Silfiasari, & Ashif Az Zhafi. (2020). Peran Pesantren dalam Pendidikan Karakter di Era Globalisasi. *Jurnal Pendidikan Islam Indonesia*, 5(1), 127–135. <https://doi.org/10.35316/jpii.v5i1.218>
 76. Mukhsin, M. (2019). Strategi Peningkatan Mutu Di Era Otonomi Pendidikan. *JUPE : Jurnal Pendidikan Mandala*. <https://doi.org/10.36312/jupe.v4i5.845>
 77. Mukti, F. D. (2019). Literasi Sains Dan Pendidikan Karakter Di Era Globalisasi. *Abdau: Jurnal Pendidikan Madrasah Ibtidaiyah*. <https://doi.org/10.36768/abdau.v1i1.1>
 78. Muniroh, S., Soedjarwo, S., & Roesminingsih, E. (2022). Pengaruh Kemampuan Manajerial dan Supervisi Kepala Madrasah Terhadap Kinerja Guru. *JDMP (Jurnal Dinamika Manajemen Pendidikan)*, 7(1), 24–38. <https://doi.org/10.26740/jdmp.v7n1.p24-38>
 79. Naisabur, C. A. P., & Kiki, K. (2022). Entrepreneurship, Kepribadian Dan Gaya Kepemimpinan Islam. *Riesyha: Riset Ekonomi Syariah Dan ...*, 1(1), 37–49.
 80. Ningsih, S. P., & Isjoni, A. (2021). Pengaruh Kinerja Guru Terhadap Hasil Belajar Siswa Kelas XI Pada Mata Pelajaran Sejarah Berbasis Daring di SMA Negeri 5 Pekanbaru. *Jurnal Pendidikan Tambusai*, 3(3), 8037–8044.
 81. Nur' Afifah, N. A. (2022). Penerapan Pendekatan Metakognitif untuk Meningkatkan Kemampuan Siswa Kelas V SD dalam Memodelkan Soal Cerita Matematika. *Journal on Education*, 05(01), 1356–1371.
 82. Okoye, K., Nganji, J. T., Escamilla, J., Fung, J. M., & Hosseini, S. (2022). Impact of global government investment on education and research development: A comparative analysis and demystifying the science, technology, innovation, and education conundrum. *Global Transitions*, 4, 11–27. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.glt.2022.10.001>
 83. Pertiwi, P. D., Pujiastuti, H., & Fathurohman, M. (2022). Implementasi Pendekatan Metakognitif dalam Pembelajaran Matematika: Systematic Literature Review. *Edukatif : Jurnal Ilmu Pendidikan*, 4(6), 7904–7918. <https://doi.org/10.31004/edukatif.v4i6.4285>
 84. Pramana, C., Chamidah, D., Suyatno, S., Renadi, F., & Syaharuddin, S. (2021). Strategies to Improved Education Quality in Indonesia: A Review. *Turkish Online Journal of Qualitative Inquiry (TOJQI)*, 12(3), 1977–1994.
 85. Putri, A. N., & Muhartati, E. (2019). Keterampilan Proses Sains Awal Mahasiswa Pendidikan Biologi Pada Matakuliah Biologi Umum. *Pedagogi Hayati*. <https://doi.org/10.31629/ph.v2i2.844>
 86. Rahayu, P. P., & Agustina, M. T. (2022). Kepemimpinan Dilihat dari Perspektif Psikologi: Literature Review. *JIIP-Jurnal Ilmiah Ilmu Pendidikan*, 5(9), 3676–3685. <https://doi.org/10.54371/jiip.v5i9.902>
 87. Rahma, D. M., Supriadi, B., & Handayani, D. (2020). Keterampilan Proses Sains Terintegrasi Siswa Kelas Xi Pada Materi Medan Magnet. *Webinar Pendidikan Fisika 2020*, 5(1), 22–26.
 88. Rahmawati, S. (2023). Dampak Kinerja Guru Terhadap Motivasi Belajar Siswa Kelas Iv The Impact Of Teacher Performance On Class Iv Students '. *AL – KAFF: Jurnal Sosial Humaniora*, 1(2), 172–181.
 89. Ranjeeni, K., Truong, C., & Kober, R. (2023). Managerial Ability and Just-in-Time Inventory Management. *SSRN Electronic Journal*, (April). <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4325002>
 90. Revati Ramrao Rautrao, & Chandrakant Hake. (2022). A Critical Study of The Implementation of Innovations For Higher Education. *East Asian Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 1(4), 643–656. <https://doi.org/10.55927/eajmr.v1i4.442>
 91. Rivas, S. F., Saiz, C., & Ossa, C. (2022). Metacognitive Strategies and Development of Critical Thinking in Higher Education. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13(June). <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.913219>
 92. Riyadi, S., Ansori, A., Ramli, A., Dewi, R. A. P. K., Dewi, R. A. P. K., & Hendrajaya, H. (2023). The Effect of Principal Managerial and Professionalism of Teachers on the Implementation of School-Based Management. *Journal on Education*, 5(4), 12198–12203. <https://doi.org/10.31004/joe.v5i4.2181>
 93. Roa, G. R., & Fajardo, M. T. M. (2022). Science Process Skills Survey as Input to Instructional Materials Development. *American Journal of Educational Research*, 10(12),

- 697–701. <https://doi.org/10.12691/education-10-12-6>
94. Rogers, H. (2022). The State of Global Learning Poverty: 2022 Update. CONFERENCE EDITION, 66–73.
95. Rohman, A. A., Yuniarti, S., & Permatasari, B. I. (2018). Pengaruh Metakognisi Dan Kreativitas Terhadap Kemampuan Pemecahan Masalah Matematis Siswa Kelas X Ips Sma Negeri 4 Balikpapan Tahun Ajaran 2017/2018. *De Fermat : Jurnal Pendidikan Matematika*. <https://doi.org/10.36277/defermat.v1i2.23>
96. Rozaq, A. K., Basri, B., & Indah, I. (2022). Kiai's Leadership in Strengthening Santri's Moderation Attitude in Islamic Boarding Schools. *Nidhomul Haq: Jurnal Manajemen Pendidikan Islam*, 7(2), 284–294. <https://doi.org/10.31538/ndh.v7i2.2322>
97. Rupnidah, R., & Eliza, D. (2022). Analisis Kemampuan Manajerial Kepala Sekolah Taman Kanak-Kanak. *Jurnal Basicedu*, 6(3), 4653–4662. <https://doi.org/10.31004/basicedu.v6i3.2826>
98. Sadali, S. (2020). Eksistensi Pesantren Sebagai Lembaga Pendidikan Islam. *Atta'dib Jurnal Pendidikan Agama Islam*, 1(2), 53–70. <https://doi.org/10.30863/attadib.v1i2.964>
99. Said, A. (2018). Kepemimpinan Kepala Sekolah Dalam Melestarikan Budaya Mutu Sekolah. *Journal EVALUASI*. <https://doi.org/10.32478/evaluasi.v2i1.77>
100. Saini, G., & Shabnam. (2021). Thinking Styles and Leadership Skills of Managers on Organizational Productivity. *IGI Global*, (April), 448–458. <https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-7998-3811-1.ch022>
101. Samitra, D., & Kristiawan, M. (2016). Keterampilan Proses Sains Dan Sikap Ilmiah Calon Guru Biologi Pada Mata Kuliah Zoologi Invertebrata. *BIOEDUSAINS: Jurnal Pendidikan Biologi Dan Sains*, 4, 1–23.
102. Sartika, L., Widayatsih, T., & Rahman, A. (2023). Pengaruh Kompetensi Manajerial Dan Kompetensi Supervisi Kepala Sekolah Terhadap Kinerja Guru. *Jurnal On Education*, 05(03), 6802–6812. Retrieved from <https://jonedu.org/index.php/joe/article/view/1465>
103. Setyaningrum, D. U., & ... (2020). Proses Metakognisi Siswa SMP dalam Pemecahan Masalah Perbandingan Senilai dan Berbalik Nilai. *Mosharafa: Jurnal ...*
104. Silva, M. (2021). The Relationship between Managerial Skills and Teaching Effectiveness of Elementary School Teachers. *International Journal of Educational Management and Development Studies*, 1(1), 1–19. <https://doi.org/10.53378/346083>
105. Sonmez Cakir, F., & Adiguzel, Z. (2020). Analysis of Leader Effectiveness in Organization and Knowledge Sharing Behavior on Employees and Organization. *SAGE Open*, 10(1). <https://doi.org/10.1177/2158244020914634>
106. Suárez-Orozco, M. M. (2005). Rethinking education in the global era. *Phi Delta Kappan*, 87(3), 209–212. <https://doi.org/10.1177/003172170508700310>
107. Sugiyanto, S., & Ruknan, R. (2020). Pengaruh Kepemimpinan, Keterampilan Manajerial, Dan Pengambilan Keputusan Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan Direktorat Jenderal Paud Dan Pendidikan Masyarakat *Jurnal Lentera Pendidikan Pusat ...*, 5(1), 37–46.
108. Sukarno, & Musyafa, A. (2021). AM Analysis of Metacognition Ability and Critical Thinking Skills of Students in Integrated Islamic Education Institutions. *INNOVATIO: Journal for Religious Innovation Studies*, 21(1), 1–17. <https://doi.org/10.30631/innovatio.v21i1.124>
109. Sukarno, & Widdah, M. El. (2020). The effect of students' metacognition and digital literacy in virtual lectures during the covid-19 pandemic on achievement in the "Methods and strategies on physics learning" course. *Jurnal Pendidikan IPA Indonesia*. <https://doi.org/10.15294/jpii.v9i4.25332>
110. Suparno. (2018). Problematika Dan Tantangan Pendidikan Pondok Pesantren Di Era Informasi. *FIKROH: Jurnal Penelitian Dan Ilmu Pendidikan*, 11(Vol 11 No 1 (2018)), 79–90. Retrieved from <https://jurnal.stai-alazharmenganti.ac.id/index.php/fikroh/article/view/35>
111. Susilawati, S., & Misbah, M. (2022). Islamic Boarding School Development: A Review from Management Reshuffle. *Pedagonal: Jurnal Ilmiah Pendidikan*, 6(1), 56–67. <https://doi.org/10.55215/pedagonal.v6i1.4952>
112. Tan, M., & Bodovski, K. (2020). Compensating for Family Disadvantage: An Analysis of the Effects of Boarding School on Chinese Students' Academic Achievement. *FIRE: Forum for International Research in Education*, 6(3), 36–57. <https://doi.org/10.32865/fire202063224>

113. Ting, I. W. K., Tebourbi, I., Lu, W. M., & Kweh, Q. L. (2021). The effects of managerial ability on firm performance and the mediating role of capital structure: evidence from Taiwan. *Financial Innovation*, 7(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40854-021-00320-7>
114. Usman, A. A., Hala, Y., & Pagarra, H. (2018). Hubungan Antara Kemampuan Metakognisi, Motivasi, Dan Kesiapan Mental Dengan Hasil Belajar Biologi Siswa Kelas XI IPA SMA Negeri Di Kabupaten Gowa. *Journal of Biological Education*.
115. Wilis, R., Adi, B., & Sunarno, W. (2023). Improving students ' metacognitive abilities and creative thinking skills through STEM-based online learning Abstract: JPBI (*Jurnal Pendidikan Biologi Indonesia*), 9(1), 90–102.
116. Yasinta, R., Haryani, S., Sumarti, S. S., & Harjono, H. (2023). Analisis Kemampuan Metakognisi Peserta Didik pada Penggunaan Lembar Kerja Peserta Didik Berbasis PjBL Materi Elektrolit dan Nonelektrolit. *Jurnal Inovasi Pendidikan Kimia*, 17(1), 49–56. <https://doi.org/10.15294/jipk.v17i1.32223>